

UDK 576.72:895:599.75

**INFECTION OF DONKEYS IN NORTHERN KARAKALPAKSTAN WITH
FASCIOLA GIGANTICA (COBBOLD, 1855)**

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Enter. Today, in our republic, particular attention is paid to the study of helminths of domestic and farm animals and the diseases they cause. In this regard, among other things, on the basis of the program measures implemented in this direction, the types of helminths that parasitize animals have been determined; the negative effects of helminthosis on the animal body have been detected and the control of the number of parasites have been achieved. In our republic, various diseases have a negative impact on the development of the livestock sector. Among such diseases, helminthiasis, including fasciolosis, is of particular importance. The causative agents of these diseases parasitize the bile ducts and gall bladder of animals and cause serious physiological changes in the host's organism. Animals may appear healthy in outer space; therefore preventive measures are not taken. As a result, the growth and development of young animals slow down, sometimes causing their death.

Based on this, determining the level of infestation of donkeys with helminths in the territory of the Republic of Karakalpakstan and developing the scientific basis of prevention of helminthosis acquire important scientific and practical importance.

In this regard, helminths that cause dangerous diseases in all branches of livestock breeding, including helminths belonging to the Trematoda class, are spread, and occupy a special place in veterinary practice. It is important to determine their spreading, diversity of species in different natural and climatic conditions, and to improve methods of combating them.

In the territory of the Republic of Karakalpakstan, there are very few scientific research studies on the fauna, ecology and distribution of donkey trematodes (Shakarboev, 2009).

The purpose of this work is to study the level of infection of donkeys with *Fasciola gigantica* (Cobbold, 1855) trematode belonging to the Fasciolidae family in the conditions of Karakalpakstan.

Research material and methods. Materials for research work have been collected in the territory of the Republic of Karakalpakstan (Fig. 1). During this period, academic (Scryabin, 1928) 31 heads of donkeys were examined by the method of complete and incomplete helminthological examination.

In addition, 156 fecal samples were examined using helminthocaprological methods. Morphological signs, parasite localization and hosts were focused on determining the species composition of helminths found during the research conducted in the Republic of Karakalpakstan (Ivashkin, Dvoynos, 1984).

In the analysis of the research results, the indicators of invasion extent (IE) and intensity of invasion (II) of damage of donkeys were taken into account.

Research results and their analysis. According to the results of the research, *Fasciola gigantica* species was found in the examined donkeys, and it was determined that it belongs to Plathelminthes type, Trematoda class, Fasciolida family, Fasciolidae family, *Fasciola* genus.

According to the results of the conducted research, it was observed that the extent of infestation with *Fasciola gigantica* in the body of donkeys: biliary tract, gall bladder, liver is 6.4%, and the intensity of invasion is 3-19 copies.

Figure 1. Map of the research area.

▲ - Stationary studies ; ● - route studies

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|----------------------|------------------------|
| 1. The city of Nukus | 10. Nukus region |
| 2. Amu Darya region | 11. Takyatosh region |
| 3. Beruny region | 12. Takhtakupir region |
| 4. Buzatov region | 13. Turtkul region |
| 5. Kanlikul region | 14. Khodjeyli region |
| 6. Korauzak region | 15. Chimboi region |
| 7. Kegeyli region | 16. Shumanoy region |
| 8. Qongirot region | 17. Ellikkala region |
| 9. Muynok fogs | |

Fasciola gigantica is a biohelminth according to its developmental cycle and develops in the presence of an intermediate host. Freshwater mollusks belonging to the Lymnaeidae family act as intermediate hosts (Ivashkin, Dvoynos, 1984).

Morphological features of the species *Fasciola gigantica* were studied during the conducted research. According to its morphological features, the body of *Fasciola gigantica* is elongated and reaches 30-75 mm in length.

Conclusion. In the territory of the Republic of Karakalpakstan, the infection of donkeys with *Fasciola gigantica* trematode was studied. In the conditions of Karakalpakstan, it was found that the extent of infestation of donkeys with *Fasciola gigantica* trematode is 6.4% and the intensity of invasion is 3-19 copies.

Figure 2. *Fasciolagigantic* (Cobbold, 1855) (original)

Used literature

1. Ivashkin V.M., Dvoinos G.M. Determinant of helminths in horses. Kiev: Naukova Dumka, 1984. – P. 7-16.
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3. Shakarboev E.B. Trematodes of vertebrates of Uzbekistan (species composition, circulation routes and ecological and biological features): Diss. ... Doctor of Biological Sciences. - Tashkent: IZ AN RUz, 2009. - 243 p.